

DWR mixed crops and hispa incidence ($r = -0.509$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 14$), but positive in the case of the long-horned cricket ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.01$, $df = 14$).

The change in cropping pattern (increased MV boro rice cropping in DWR areas) positively influenced YSB and probably also favored hispa. Boro cropping favored the establishment of first generation YSB moths (following diapause in winter) in boro rice during Feb and Mar. Irrigated boro cropping

also reduced or eliminated high temperature stress ($>33^\circ\text{C}$) coupled with low relative humidity ($<70\%$) on the YSB during Apr-Jun, which favored population buildup.

YSB seems to concentrate in DWR following boro rice harvest. Hispa prefers young rice plants. That explains its concentration in fields with only DWR. Ripening aus rice probably influenced the high incidence of long-horned crickets in aus rice + DWR fields. ■

Dispersal range of rice insect pests under natural conditions in the Philippines

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We estimated the dispersal range of rice insect pests in the Philippines using a low-cost method that measures rather than manipulates natural movement. Conventional approaches (such as mark-recapture) often require handling the insects in ways that could significantly affect behavior.

During the fallow period between wet and dry season crops in early 1982, we located an isolated 1.5-ha field in Nueva Ecija where IR52 had been grown under irrigation from a shallow well pump. Except for a similar field one km west, this field had the only standing rice within several kilometers.

As the crop approached maturity, we established two parallel transects of kerosene light traps running eastward, 200 m apart. The traps were positioned within the field and at 5, 20, 50, 95, 170, 290, and 485 m into the fallow area, a geometric progression that provided greatest resolution near the field. The lamps were lit every night for more than a month, until harvest in late February.

We analyzed catches of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Paraponyx fluctuosalis*, and *Naranga aenescens* from 19 Jan until they began to rise after the fallow area was planted (see table). Catches of other species were too low to analyze.

The best-fitting first- or second-degree nonlinear equations are given in the table and illustrated for yellow stem borer (YSB) males in the figure. Catches declined with distance from the field. Dispersal distances were calculated from regressions corrected for background density (i.e., insects emerging from rice stubble, other host plants, and distant, scattered sources). We estimated background density from catches in four light traps at two sites 4.5 km to the east and the south. Corrected equations were integrated and rotated about the origin (in other words, assuming that movement was similar in all directions).

Toxicology of insecticides to rice leaffolder (LF) larvae

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We evaluated the toxicology of three commonly used insecticides: an organophosphate, a carbamate, and a synthetic pyrethroid. Fourth-instar LF

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis larvae from cultures reared from moths collected in Laguna, Philippines, were topically treated at 15 d old with 0.5 μl of each insecticide solution, using an Arnold Microapplicator. Control larvae were treated with acetone.

Results are given in the table. The probit lines fitted the data well, and the insects used were found to be homogeneous.

In the test for parallelism, probit lines for BPMC and cypermethrin were found to

be parallel; diazinon significantly deviated from these two lines (see figure). The parallel lines satisfy the condition of similarity and are thus comparable.

Cypermethrin was about 250 times more toxic than BPMC. This implies that a much smaller dose of cypermethrin is required to cause LF mortality.

These results can be used as baseline data for insecticide resistance studies. ■

Probit lines of insecticides topically applied on the fourth-instar leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae.

Probit analysis of diazinon, BPMC, and cypermethrin on 4th-instar larvae of rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	Fiducial limits (ppm)	LD ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{larva}$)	Regression equation
Diazinon	259.8	215.5 - 310.1	0.13	$y = 5.07 + 2.70(x-12.44)$
BPMC	9896.6	6519.1 - 15264.4	4.95	$y = 4.91 + 0.95(x-13.97)$
Cypermethrin	40.6	23.0 - 141.1	0.02	$y = 4.83 + 1.11(x-11.46)$

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) incidence in Assam

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In May 1990, RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino was observed to attack

traditional rice variety Maibi sown 20 Mar 1990 as summer rainfed rice on a 15-20% slope in the hill district of Karbi Anglong, Assam. This is the first report of RWM attacking rice in upland fields. The insect has been recorded earlier on rice crops in the plains and low-lying areas. ■